

REVIEW ARTICLE

Prominent botanists of Central Asia: Vvedensky Aleksei Ivanovich (1898–1972)

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ABSTRACT

This article honours the memory of the outstanding taxonomist and tireless researcher of the flora of Central Asia, Aleksei Ivanovich Vvedensky, the founder of the most extensive Central Asian herbarium collection, the author of monographic revisions in ‘Flora of the USSR’, the editor and author of the six volume edition of ‘Flora of Uzbekistan’, the ‘Conspectus Florae Asiae Mediae’, and various taxonomic publications Vvedensky described dozens of new genera and hundreds of new species of vascular plants from Central Asia.

Key words: *Allium*; *Iris*, *Eremurus*; bibliography; Vvedensky; taxonomy; Middle Asia

Aleksei Ivanovich Vvedensky was born on March 7, 1898, in the city of Penza (Russia) in the family of a teacher. He discovered his interest in botany early in school. The famous Penzini botanists Profs. I.I. Sprygin and M.G. Popov played an eminent role in the career of their young and energetic student. Under their guidance, Aleksei acquired his first skills in herbarization, biodocumentation, and identification of vascular plants (Butkov et al. 1968).

The professional development of A.I. Vvedensky took place against the backdrop of the violent revolutionary events of 1917–1920, the fall of the Russian Empire as a result of revolutions, the First World War and the Civil War. In 1917, Vvedensky, still very young, became a member of the Penza Society for Natural Sciences, whose chairman was I.I. Sprygin. The following year, his first publication appeared: ‘News and the rarity of the Penza flora’ (1918). In January 1919, Vvedensky was appointed head of the

Herbarium of the Penza Provincial Natural Historical Museum. A year later, he began working at the Penza Zoological and Botanical Garden, which was united with the Museum, while still heading the herbarium and holding the full-time position of taxonomist.

In 1920, by order of the government, a large group of Russian scientists was sent to Tashkent with the mission of creating a higher educational institution in Turkestan. Together with I.I. Sprygin, M.G. Popov, E.P. Korovin, and four other employees of the Penza Museum, Vvedensky arrived to Tashkent and, among the large group of botanists and soil scientists, became actively involved in organizing the botanical department. The Penza botanists who moved to Tashkent were called the ‘Group of Sprygin’.

The Department of Botany they created became part of the Physics and Mathematics Faculty of the Turkestan People’s University (since 1924 the Central Asian State University; since 1960 Tashkent State University; and

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currently the National University of Uzbekistan). Since the 1920s, many leading botanists of that time began to work there, including R.I. Abolin, A.A. Baranov, A.V. Blagoveschensky, V.P. Drobov, M.G. Popov, E.P. Korovin, M.V. Kultiasov, N.D. Leonov, I.A. Raikova, M.M. Sovetkina and others (Tojibaev et al. 2020). Over time, it was this department that would later serve as a scientific centre for the development of plant science in Central Asia. The Tashkent group of young and talented botanists introduced the scientific world to hundreds of new plant species, as well as to the unique features of the vegetation of Central Asia.

In Tashkent, throughout the 1920s, Vvedensky combined organizational work with scientific research at the university, which may explain his relatively late graduation. Vvedensky completed his higher education in 1929 with the thesis entitled 'Central Asian *Gagea reticulata* s.l. alliance and its path of evolution' (handwritten manuscript, 1929). At that time, Vvedensky worked as a researcher at the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics, head of the herbarium of the Botanical Garden, expert in the Botanical Garden, and head of the herbarium of the Central Asian University (Lipschitz 1947).

The special contribution of A.I. Vvedensky was the creation of the University Herbarium in 1920, originally called Herbarium Horti Botanici Universitatis Asiae Mediae (subsequently Herbarium Universitatis Taschkenticae, acronym TAK) which he himself headed since 1925. From 1923 to 1934, twenty issues of 'Shedae ad Herbarium Florae Asiae Mediae' were published (Vasilchenko, Vassilieva, 1975). The herbarium was created from the collections of the Bureau of Soil and Botanical Research, established in 1909. Much later, in early 1988, the University Herbarium was merged with the Herbarium of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR (Pratov and Adylov 1996). The TASH Herbarium (Institute of Botany, Tashkent) (Pratov and Adylov 1996), which already existed at that time, was originally based on the collections of the plant resources

sector of the Committee of Sciences created in 1936. At first, in the united herbarium, the university and academic collections existed in parallel, with their own particular nomenclature, and were located in different premises. The collections were merged and reorganized by T.A. Adylov, who was the curator of the Herbarium from 1972 to 1988, in a process of painstaking work. Later, A.I. Vvedensky brought the number of sheets in this collection to around half a million. Under his leadership, there was established a practice of an exchange of duplicates of herbarium specimens with the then Soviet and foreign herbaria, such as W (Vienna), P (Paris), K and BM (London). At that time, this required not only a huge organizational effort, but also the firm authority of Vvedensky.

In working with the herbarium collection, Vvedensky was exceptionally meticulous and pedantic. According to the memoirs of T.A. Adylov, when they brought freshly collected plants, Vvedensky immediately sent the collectors to dry the plant material before proceeding with the identification procedure. At the same time, he did not trust anyone with a significant part of the herbarization work, and preferred to perform it himself, or only with reliable employees (V.K. Pazij, S.S. Kovalevskaya, N.B. Nikiforova, and others). Vvedensky also actively participated in field research and collected huge numbers of herbarium specimens. The samples collected by him personally constituted a significant part of the material he used in the preparation of his major scientific publications. So, when working on the publication 'Herbarium Florae Asiae Mediae' (1924–1928), Vvedensky utilized over 25,000 herbarium sheets, a significant portion of which were collected in field expeditions led by Vvedensky.

In 1935, A.I. Vvedensky was awarded the Candidate of Biological Sciences degree without the need of a dissertation defense (based on the totality of his published works) and was awarded the title of associate professor. In 1943, he was elected a corresponding member of the Academy of

Sciences of Uzbekistan. Vvedensky established the Systematics of Vascular Plants Laboratory at the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, which he headed from 1950 to 1958.

Despite problems with his health that arose with aging, he continued to lead and participate in many field expeditions to various regions throughout Central Asia (Fig. 1). Although his mobility decreased with age and the expeditions became fewer, he nevertheless was collecting large numbers of samples during field work. Botanists dealing with the scientific heritage of A.I. Vvedensky note the broad spectrum of his floral interests. He was a known expert for all plant groups, from ferns to composites.

In 1923, A.I. Vvedensky published the 'Identification of the Plants of Tashkent: an illustrated guide to the identification of wild vascular spore and flowering plants' (Popov 1923), which focused on the plant diversity of the mountainous surroundings Tashkent city (Tashkentskiy Ala-Too). In fact, this publication served as a textbook for teaching lab classes on the taxonomy of flowering plants at the university, which took place at that time in the vicinity of the village of Kaplanbek (near Tashkent, now belonging to Kazakhstan). Due to the additional coverage of areas with high plant diversity, such as the vicinities of Humsan (Ugam Range), Chimgan (Chatkal Range), and Burch Mullah (Koksuv Range), it became an often used handbook for many Central Asian botanists. The textbook focused on seven families (Araceae, Lemnaceae, Juncaceae, Liliaceae, Amaryllidaceae, Iridaceae and Orchidaceae), 20 genera and 86 species. In the following year, Vvedensky (1924) critically reviewed 150 species for the Herbarium Florae Asiae Mediae. For the Flora of Turkmenistan (vol. 1, 1932), Vvedensky contributed the families Liliaceae (except *Tulipa*, *Eremurus*, *Asparagus*), Amaryllidaceae and Araceae, totaling 15 genera and 74 species. Vvedensky also contributed to the multi-volume Flora of the USSR (30 volumes, 1934–1964), for which the team of authors was selected with great care. He revised the genera *Bromus*

(Vvedensky et al. 1934), *Tulipa*, *Allium*, *Ungernia*, *Iris*, and *Juno* (Vvedensky 1935); the Rutaceae and the genera *Biebersteinia* and *Erodium* (Vvedensky 1949), *Pedicularis* (Vvedensky 1955), contributing to the Flora of the USSR in total morphological descriptions of 518 species. To the six-volume edition of the Flora of Uzbekistan (1941–1963), he contributed the Eriocaulonaceae, Liliaceae, Amaryllidaceae, Iridaceae (Schreder 1941), Caryophyllaceae (Vvedensky 1953), Brassicaceae and *Rosa* (Vvedensky 1955). Rutaceae, Lythraceae and Onagraceae (Vvedensky 1959), Convolvulaceae, Lamiaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Valerianaceae and Campanulaceae (Vvedensky 1961), and the dichotomous identification key for Asteraceae (Vvedensky 1962). A total of 714 species were referenced by Vvedensky in the Flora of Uzbekistan. The Flora of Uzbekistan included information on 4148 vascular plants of Uzbekistan and in 1962 was awarded the prestigious state scientific prize named after Abu Rayhan Beruni (Sennikov 2016). For the ten-volume Flora of Tajikistan (Ovchinnikov 1963), Vvedensky contributed the Araceae, Liliaceae, Amaryllidaceae, and Iridaceae (28 genera, 236 species). For the first two volumes of the 'Conspectus Florae Asiae Mediae,' he contributed the Potamogetonaceae, Zosteraceae, Najadaceae, and Pteridophyta (Vvedensky 1968) and Liliaceae (Vvedensky 1971).

Vvedensky devoted much attention to the ornamental bulbous plants of Central Asia. Using the living collection of the Tashkent Botanical Garden (TBG), he monographically revised the genera *Tulipa*, *Eremurus*, *Fritillaria* and *Iris*. He made a thorough revision of the genus *Allium* L., a favorite genus that he worked on throughout his life. The taxonomic revisions by Vvedensky were adopted by leading specialists from abroad. His revision of the genus *Allium* L. was appreciated and accepted by R.V. Kamelin (1973) and Per Wendelbo (1971). In his work with *Allium*, Vvedensky mainly used fresh plant materials of the TBG, maintaining close collaboration with the local staff. One result of this close

collaboration was the establishment in the TBG of a section with bulbous geophytes, mainly from the genera *Tulipa* and *Allium*. At one point, this collection consisted of about 6,000 wild species and horticultural varieties (*Tulipa*, *Eremurus*, *Iris*, *Juno*, *Crocus*, *Colchicum*, *Fritillaria*, etc.), of which more than 2000 were wild and garden tulips. In the collection of the TBG, preference was given to wild Central Asian tulips (70% of the area was occupied by wild species and about 30% by various varieties of cultivated tulips, mainly Dutch (Tojibaev 2011).

An article dedicated to Vvedensky's 70th birthday (Butkov et al. 1968) noted the high level of his knowledge of the flora of Central Asia, as well as his great professional erudition and excellent knowledge of botanical nomenclature and geography.

According to oral communication by O.V. Cherneva, A.I. Vvedensky dreamed of compiling a map of ancient soils (variegated outcrops) of the Central Asian region, and 'populating' the outcrops of such soils in Central Asia with ancient plant communities. This task was largely due to Vvedensky's specific scientific approach of involving specialists from all related fields (geographers, geologists, soil scientists, zoologists).

In 1968, the first volume of a 10-volume monograph on the flora of Central Asia appeared (Vvedensky 1968–1993), which was essentially a critical regional flora overview summarizing almost 100 years of research, as well as revisions of the floras of neighbouring to Central Asia regions Iran and Afghanistan. In fact, this multi-volume work served as the basis for the new Flora of Uzbekistan (Sennikov et al. 2016).

In addition to the abovementioned multi-volume publications, A.I. Vvedensky was the editor of the following botanical reports: 18 issues of 'Botanical materials of Herbarium of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the UzSSR' (1941–1948); vols. III–XI 'Flora of Kyrgyzstan' (1951–1965), 'Key of the wild plant species of the Hungarian steppe' (1960).

The following monographs were published under the editorship of Vvedensky:

Lapin A.M. 'Key of the plants of the Tashkent oasis, Part 1' (1938);

Korovin E.P. 'Illustrated monograph of the genus *Ferula*' (1947);

Bondarenko O.N. 'Key of the highest plants of the Karakalpakia' (1964);

Puchkova E.G. 'Species of the *Chaetodon* section and its position in the genus *Astragalus*' (1967) and many others.

As a university professor, A.I. Vvedensky supervised undergraduate and graduate students in the areas of floristics, plant taxonomy, and phytogeography with his impressive encyclopedic knowledge. Among his students are: A.Ya. Butkov – one of the leading phytocenologists of Uzbekistan; Z.P. Botschantzeva – a leading scientist on tulips in Central Asia and adjacent territories; S.S. Kovalevskaja – a famous expert on many leading taxonomic groups of the flora of Central Asia, including Asteraceae; V.K. Pazij – an eminent university lecturer who described more than 40 new species from the families Fabaceae, Poaceae, Euphorbiaceae, and Lamiaceae; O.V. Cherneva – an expert in *Cousinia* Cass. and *Jurinea* Cass. In working with his students, Vvedensky had a unique pedagogical style of teaching the students how to conduct scientific research and write the papers. His approach was fascinating and highly motivating. However, Vvedensky became notably disappointed when some of his students, having undergone an extensive training, moved from Tashkent to other scientific institutions of the former Soviet Union republics.

In total, A.I. Vvedensky's botanical contribution to the flora of Central Asia comprises the description of 9 new genera, 20 new sections, about 300 new species, more than 50 new combinations, amounting to more than 1,500 original descriptions of wild plants (Fig. 3.) (Table 1, 2) (Butkov et al. 1968). His invaluable contribution to science was the creation of the TASH Herbarium. Vvedensky educated a large number of talented plant taxonomists. He was the editor of a number of

famous botanical publications and was one of the first to recognize the uniqueness and diversity of the Central Asian flora and its connections with other floristic regions of the world. Without a doubt, Aleksei Ivanovich Vvedensky deserves enormous gratitude and respect from botanists around the world.

A.I. Vvedensky was married and had a daughter. In interpersonal communication A.I.

seems to have been a humorous man who loved telling funny stories (Fig. 4.). Many photos have been preserved from happy gatherings with employees (Fig. 2). Other colleagues enviously joked that the Vvedensky group always had the most beautiful women.

Fig. 1. A.I. Vvedensky

Fig. 2. Social gathering, 12 Feb. 1959. A.Y. Butkov, O.V. Cherneva, A.I. Vvedensky, S.S. Kovalevskaya, S. Abdullayeva (from left to right)

On July 27, 1972, at age 74, Aleksei Ivanovich Vvedensky died in Tashkent and was buried at the Botkin cemetery.

It is difficult to overestimate the contributions of Aleksei Ivanovich Vvedensky to the development of plant systematics and the herbaria of Central Asia.

Three genera have been named in honour of Vvedensky (*Vvedenskya* Korovin, *Vvedenskyella* Botsch., *Alexeya* Pachom.), one section of *Allium* – *Vvedenskya* Kamelin and 51 species: *Centaurea vvedenskyi* Popov, *Iris vvedenskyi* Nevski ex Woronow & Popov, *Tragopogon vvedenskyi* Popov, *Psephellus vvedenskii* Sosn., *Gagea vvedenskyi* Grossh., *G. alexejana* Kamelin ex Levichev, *G. alexii* Ali & Levichev, *Juncus vvedenskyi* V.I. Krecz., *Salsola vvedenskyi* Iljin & Popov, *Haplophyllum vvedenskyi* Nevski, *Rheum vvedenskyi* Sumnev., *Polygonum vvedenskyi* Sumnev., *Elytrigia vvedenskyi* Drobow, *Ranunculus vvedenskyi* Ovcz., *Poa vvedenskyi* Drobow, *Bupleurum vvedenskyi* Manden., *Astragalus vvedenskyi* Popov, *A. alexejii* Gontsch., *Frankenian vvedenskyi* Botsch.,

Andrachne vvedenskyi Pazij, *Rosa vvedenskyi* Korotkova, *Allium vvedenskyanum* Pavlov, *Gentiana vvedenskyi* Grossh., *Acantholimon vvedenskyi* Lincz., *Aster vvedenskyi* Bondarenko, *Cousinia vvedenskyi* Tscherneva, *Asparagus vvedenskyi* Botsch., *Ephedra vvedenskyi* Pachom., *Hedysarum vvedenskyi* Korotkova, *Olgaea vvedenskyi* Iljin, *Salvia vvedenskyi* Nikitina, *Potentilla vvedenskyi* Botsch., *Saussurea vvedenskyi* Lipsch., *Scrophularia vvedenskyi* Bondarenko & Filatova, *Tulipa vvedenskyi* Botschantz., *Delphinium vvedenskyi* Pachom., *Strigosella vvedenskyi* Bondarenko & Botsch., *Draba vvedenskyi* Kovalevsk., *Scaligeria vvedenskyi* Kamelin, *Saxifraga vvedenskyi* Abdullaeva, *Viola alexejana* Kamelin & Junussov, *Alexeya vvedenskyi* Pachomova, *Rosularia vvedenskyi* U.P. Prатов, *Pseudoclausia vvedenskyi* Pachom., *Ungernia vvedenskyi* Khamidch., *Valerianella vvedenskyi* Lincz., *Scilla vvedenskyi* Pazij, *Oxytropis vvedenskyi* Filim., *Gentiana vvedenskyi* Grossh., *Lagochilus vvedenskyi* Kamelin & Zuckerw., *Silene vvedenskyi* Lazkov.

Eremurus brachystemon Vved. sp. n. — Radix paullo
 furiforme incrassata, 5-8 mm. crassa. Folia late linearia,
 exteriora ~~10-12~~ mm lata, glauca, canaliculata, carinata,
^{glabra} glabra vel ad margines carinamque sparse scabra. Caulis glaber,
 gracilis, 60-100 cm altus. Racemus latus, pluriflorus,
 cylindricus, 15-50 cm longus. Bractee villae-ciliatae, trian-
 gulares, longe et sensim attenuatae. Pedicelli patentis,
 perigonio $1\frac{1}{2}$ -2-plo longiores ut axis brunnei, ~~sub~~ apice
 articulati, fructiferi incrassati horizontaliter ~~patentes~~
^(e vivis) declinati. Perigonio campanulati ~~phyllo~~ (11-12 mm longa,
 apice pallidissime rosei, dorso sordide rosca, basi sordide rosea
 dorso pubescentia, ~~nervis~~ nervis 3-5 brunnescenti-purpureis
 percursa, post anthesin ~~reflexa~~ ^{sordide atro rosca} involuta exteriora lanceo-
 lata, interiora late-lanceolata vel ovato-lanceolata, ~~Stam-~~ Sta-
 mina aequilonga, 12-14 mm longa, filamentis rubescenti-
 brunneis (atro rufis), post anthesin subnigris, antheris brunneo-
 mimatis. Ovarium viride. Stylus aurantiaco-brunneus.
 Capsula globosa laevis, 15-18 mm lata. Semina oblique
 late alata ^{at decidua saepe}
 Habitat ^{in jugis} Hissarica (Pamiraj, terra Media).
^{Lione media}

Species affinitate incerta, staminibus brevibus et
 capsulis magnis l. comarum O. Fedtsch. ~~in mentem~~
 vocet, sed bractearum forma, perigonii fabrica, foliis
 glabris ^{atque vatis} ~~at~~ distat.

Typus: *Uccapocund* sibirica. Krasnodarskaia gubernia
 p. Bagrod *Prisel kurd.* Symp. 1937. v. 20 fl. *Uccapocund*-
icum, 67 (in herb. hort. bot. univ. St. ped. sub n° 167424
 conservatur). — Paratypus: *Uccapocund* sibirica. Krasnodarskaia gubernia
 p. p. Sugga *Main-vypa*. Krasnodarskaia gubernia. 1930. v. 3 fr. ^(in. d. 1930)

Fig. 3. Manuscript of A.I. Vvedensky with a protologue of *Eremurus brachystemon* (archive of Institute of Botany UAS).

Fig. 4. Friendly cartoon of A.I. Vvedensky, surprisingly found at the Botanical Institute of Komarov in the office of I.A. Linczewsky (Institute of Botany, Kazakh Academy of Sciences) (author is unknown). The original is kept at the Botanical Institute of Komarov (keeper is A.K. Sytin, to whom we are greatly indebted for providing this cartoon).

List of main publications of A.I. Vvedensky

1918

Новости и редкости Пензенской флоры // Труды Пензенского общества любителей естествознания и краеведения. Вып. 3–4 (1917 г.). С. 159–162.

1923

Новый род из семейства губоцветных *Phlomidopsis* // Труды Туркестанского Научного общества при Средне-Азиатском Государственном Университете. Ташкент. Вып. I. С. 119–122. (Совместно с М. Г. Поповым).

Новые виды туркестанских луков // Труды Туркестанского Научного общества при Средне-Азиатском Государственном Университете. Ташкент. Вып. I. С. 122–126.

Определитель растений окрестностей г. Ташкента, вып. I (Polypodiaceae — Urticaceae) / Под ред. М. Г. Попова. — Ташкент: Изд-во САГУ. 80 с. (Совместно с В. П. Дробовым, Е. П. Коровиным, М. В. Культиасовым, М. Г. Поповым, И. А. Райковой).

Определитель растений окрестностей г. Ташкента, вып. II (Urticaceae — Cruciferae) / Под ред. М. Г. Попова. — Ташкент: Изд-во САГУ. 80 с.

1924

Decas Alliorum novorum ex Asia Media // Ботанические материалы Гербария Главного ботанического сада РСФСР. Т. V, вып. 6. С. 89–96.

1925

Species novae e montibus Karatau Turkestanicae // Труды Туркестанского Научного общества при Средне-Азиатском Государственном Университете. Вып. II. С. 29–31.

1932

Семейство *Agaceae* // Флора Туркмении. Т. I. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. С. 233–236.

Семейство *Liliaceae* // Флора Туркмении. Т. I. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. 246–316.

1934

Descriptiones Alliorum novorum // Бюллетень Среднеазиатского государственного университета. Вып. 19. С. 119–130.

Род *Bromus* L. // Флора СССР. Т. 2. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. С. 554–583. (Совместно с В. И. Кречетовичем, С. А. Невским, В. В. Сочавой).

1935

Род *Allium* L. // Флора СССР. Т. 4. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. С. 112–280.

Род *Tulipa* L. // Флора СССР. Т. 4. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. С. 320–364.

Род *Ungernia* Bunge // Флора СССР. Т. 4. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. С. 481–485.

Род *Iris* L. (секция *Junopsis*) // Флора СССР. Т. 4. Ленинград: Изд-во Акад. наук СССР. С. 557–576.

Tulipae et Junopnes novae // Бюллетень Среднеазиатского государственного университета. Ташкент, Вып. 21. С. 147–152.

1937

Новый род *Korovinia* из сем. Зонтичных // Труды Ботанического института АН СССР. I сер., 4: 272–273. (Совместно с С.А. Невским).

Новый род *Platytaenia* из сем. Зонтичных // Труды Ботанического института АН СССР. I сер., 4: 270–271. (Совместно с С. А. Невским).

1941

Семейство *Egiosaulonaceae* // Флора Узбекистана. Т. 1. Ташкент: Изд-во Акад. наук УзССР. С. 381–382.

Семейство *Liliaceae* // Флора Узбекистана. Т. 1. Ташкент: Изд-во Акад. наук УзССР. С. 394–495.

Семейство *Amaryllidaceae* // Флора Узбекистана. Т. 1. Ташкент: Изд-во Акад. наук УзССР. С. 495–502.

Семейство *Iridaceae* // Флора Узбекистана. Т. 1. Ташкент: Изд-во Акад. наук УзССР. С.502–522.

Диагнозы новых видов // Флора Узбекистана. Т. 1. Ташкент: Изд-во Акад. наук УзССР. С. 537, 540–545.

Новые виды растений // Ботанические материалы гербария института Ботаники Академии наук Узбекской ССР. Т. III. С. 3–20. (Совместно с В. П. Бочанцевым).

Новый род семейства губоцветных // Ботанические материалы Гербария Ботанического института имени В. Л. Комарова Академии наук СССР. Т. IX, вып. 2. С. 54–55.

1946

Новые лилейные Таджикистана // Ботанические материалы Гербария Ботанического института имени В. Л. Комарова Академии наук СССР. Т. IX, вып. 4–12. С. 232–247.

Новый вид рода *Androsace* из Памира // Ботанические материалы Гербария Ботанического института имени В. Л. Комарова Академии наук СССР. Т. IX, вып. 4–12, С. 213–214. (Совместно с П. Н. Овчинниковым).

1948

Новые виды рода *Haplophyllum* // Ботанические материалы Гербария Института ботаники и Зоологии АН УзССР, 10: 3–5.

Новые крестоцветные из Средней Азии // Ботанические материалы Гербария Института ботаники и Зоологии АН УзССР, 12: 3–12.

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Род *Juno* Tratt. // Определитель растений Средней Азии. Т. 2. Ташкент: Изд-во «Фан» УзССР. С. 132–139.

Table 1. List of new vascular plant genera (9 genera) described by A.I. Vvedensky (including as a co-author) between 1922–1987 (data from IPNI 2022)

Scientific name	Publication year	Endemic to Central Asia (POWO)	IPNI Plant Name Id
<i>Mesostemma</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	956774-1
<i>Antonina</i> Vved.	1961	non-endemic	20666-1
<i>Calispepla</i> Vved.	1952	non-endemic	21896-1
<i>Nevskiella</i> V.I. Krecz. & Vved.	1934	non-endemic	18593-1
<i>Platytaenia</i> Nevski & Vved.	1937	non-endemic	40406-1
<i>Stachyopsis</i> Popov & Vved.	1923	non-endemic	21240-1
<i>Prionotrichon</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	non-endemic	12943-1
<i>Phlomidioschema</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	21112-1
<i>Korovinina</i> Nevski & Vved.	1937	non-endemic	40141-1

Table 2. List of new vascular plant species described by A.I. Vvedensky (including as a co-author) between 1922–1987 (data from IPNI 2022).

Scientific name (taxa)	Publication year	Endemic to Central Asia (POWO)	IPNI Plant Name Id	Holotype/lectotype
<i>Acanthophyllum cyrtostegium</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978235-1	TASH001024
<i>Acanthophyllum leiostegium</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978236-1	LE
<i>Acanthophyllum ruptile</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	978237-1	TASH
<i>Allium alaicum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	527542-1	LE
<i>Allium albovianum</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	527555-1	G00165237
<i>Allium alexandrae</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	527559-1	LE
<i>Allium anisotepalum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	527606-1	LE
<i>Allium aroides</i> Popov & Vved.	1934	endemic	527628-1	TASH000334
<i>Allium brachyscapum</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	527710-1	TASH000339
<i>Allium brevidens</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	527717-1	LE
<i>Allium brevidentiforme</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	527718-1	TASH000341
<i>Allium clausum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	527844-1	TASH000350
<i>Allium confragosum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	527864-1	TASH000351
<i>Allium crystallinum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	527892-1	TASH000356
<i>Allium dasphyllum</i> Vved.	1925	endemic	527914-1	TASH000359
<i>Allium dictyoscordum</i> Vved.	1924	non-endemic	527944-1	LE
<i>Allium dodecadontum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	527952-1	TASH000362
<i>Allium dolichomischum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	527954-1	TASH000364
<i>Allium dolichostylum</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	527955-1	LE
<i>Allium drepanophyllum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	527961-1	TASH000367
<i>Allium drobovi</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	527962-1	TASH
<i>Allium dshungaricum</i> Vved.	1971	non-endemic	77177072-1	LE
<i>Allium eremoprasum</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	527992-1	TASH000380
<i>Allium eriocoleum</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	527994-1	TASH000381
<i>Allium eugeni</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528001-1	LE
<i>Allium ferganicum</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	528026-1	LE
<i>Allium filidentiforme</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	528034-1	LE
<i>Allium flavellum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	528047-1	LE
<i>Allium glaciale</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528091-1	TASH000384
<i>Allium goloskokovii</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528101-1	AA
<i>Allium gracillimum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	528110-1	TASH000386
<i>Allium gypsaceum</i> Popov & Vved.	1924	endemic	528134-1	LE
<i>Allium gypsodictyum</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	528135-1	TASH000388
<i>Allium helicophyllum</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	528146-1	TASH000391
<i>Allium hexaceras</i> Vved.	1963	endemic	528152-1	TASH000392
<i>Allium hissanicum</i> Vved.	1963	endemic	528162-1	TASH003028
<i>Allium inconspicuum</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	528191-1	TASH000395

<i>Allium incrustatum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	528192-1	LE
<i>Allium inops</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	528196-1	LE
<i>Allium insufficiens</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528198-1	LE
<i>Allium jajlae</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	528212-1	LE
<i>Allium jaxarticum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528219-1	TASH000397
<i>Allium jodanthum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528223-1	TASH000401
<i>Allium jucundum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528225-1	LE
<i>Allium komarovianum</i> Vved.	1929	non-endemic	528258-1	LE
<i>Allium kopetdagense</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	528260-1	LE
<i>Allium kujukense</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	528265-1	TASH000404
<i>Allium kunthianum</i> Vved.	1932	non-endemic	528267-1	LE
<i>Allium lasiophyllum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528287-1	LE
<i>Allium leptomorphum</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	528305-1	LE
<i>Allium lipskyanum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528321-1	TASH000408
<i>Allium litvinovii</i> Drobow ex Vved.	1932	endemic	528325-1	TASH000410
<i>Allium longiradiatum</i> (Regel) Vved.	1925	endemic	528338-1	LE
<i>Allium lutescens</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528352-1	TASH000412
<i>Allium majus</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	528377-1	TASH000419
<i>Allium margaritiferum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528384-1	TASH000423
<i>Allium marschallianum</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	528389-1	TASH000335
<i>Allium minutum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528416-1	LE
<i>Allium mogoltavicum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528426-1	TASH000427
<i>Allium monophyllum</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	528436-1	LE
<i>Allium nevskianum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528484-1	TASH000437
<i>Allium nothum</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	528500-1	TASH000438
<i>Allium ophiophyllum</i> Vved.	1928	endemic	528533-1	TASH000442
<i>Allium oreodictyum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528538-1	LE
<i>Allium oreoprasoides</i> Vved.	1925	endemic	528541-1	TASH000444
<i>Allium oreoscordum</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	528543-1	LE
<i>Allium parvulum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528588-1	LE
<i>Allium pauli</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	528596-1	LE
<i>Allium popovii</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	528642-1	TASH000450
<i>Allium praemixtum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	528653-1	TASH000451
<i>Allium pseudoflavum</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	528675-1	LE
<i>Allium pseudoseravschanicum</i> Popov & Vved.	1935	non-endemic	528679-1	LE
<i>Allium pumilum</i> Vved.	1934	non-endemic	528688-1	LE
<i>Allium rhodanthum</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	528732-1	TASH000454
<i>Allium schachimardanicum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528815-1	TASH000458
<i>Allium schugnanicum</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	528827-1	LE
<i>Allium scrobiculatum</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	528837-1	TASH000459
<i>Allium sergii</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	528850-1	MW
<i>Allium sordidiflorum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	528885-1	LE

<i>Allium stephanophorum</i> Vved.	1924	endemic	528918-1	LE
<i>Allium sulphureum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	528954-1	LE
<i>Allium svetlanae</i> Vved. ex Filim.	1982	endemic	899127-1	TASH000466
<i>Allium taciturnum</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	528964-1	TASH000471
<i>Allium taeniopetalum</i> Popov & Vved.	1934	endemic	528965-1	LE
<i>Allium trachyscordum</i> Vved.	1925	endemic	529026-1	TASH000473
<i>Allium transvestiens</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	529029-1	TASH000480
<i>Allium tythanthum</i> Vved.	1934	endemic	529071-1	TASH000482
<i>Allium ugami</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	529074-1	TASH000485
<i>Allium vavilovii</i> Popov & Vved.	1934	non-endemic	529098-1	TASH000488
<i>Allium victoris</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	529109-1	TASH000490
<i>Alyssum stenostachyum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	non-endemic	978254-1	TASH001324
<i>Androsace acrolasia</i> Vved. & Ovez.	1946	non-endemic	700154-1	TASH002598
<i>Antonina debilis</i> (Bunge) Vved.	1961	non-endemic	444843-1	LE
<i>Arabis karatavica</i> (Lipsch.) Botsch. & Vved.	1957	endemic	278325-1	LE
<i>Arabis popovii</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	278522-1	TASH001245
<i>Asparagus ferganensis</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	531103-1	TASH000563
<i>Asparagus gypsaceus</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	531133-1	TASH000567
<i>Asparagus komarovianus</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	531156-1	LE
<i>Asparagus monocladus</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	531208-1	LE
<i>Astragalus devestitus</i> Pazij & Vved.	1952	endemic	477126-1	TASH001651
<i>Astragalus drobovii</i> Popov & Vved.	1926	endemic	477213-1	TASH001660
<i>Astragalus lachnolobus</i> Kovalevsk. & Vved.	1955	endemic	478198-1	TASH001714
<i>Astragalus leptophysus</i> Vved.	1959	endemic	478311-1	TASH001726
<i>Astragalus rubescens</i> Kovalevsk. & Vved.	1955	endemic	479585-1	TASH001788
<i>Astragalus stenophysus</i> Vved. & Zakirov	1952	endemic	479951-1	TASH001797
<i>Astragalus thaumatothamnus</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	480190-1	TASH001834
<i>Astragalus uninodis</i> Popov & Vved.	1922	endemic	480379-1	TASH001840
<i>Bellevalia inconspicua</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	531813-1	LE
<i>Calispepla aegacanthoides</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	483026-1	TASH003683
<i>Campyloptera carnea</i> (Banks & Sol.) Botsch. & Vved.	1955	non-endemic	279891-1	LE
<i>Cerastium bungeanum</i> Vved.	1953	non-endemic	152129-1	LE
<i>Cerastium taschkenticum</i> Adylov & Vved.	1971	endemic	152692-1	TASH000931
<i>Chrysanthemum santoanum</i> Krasch., Popov & Vved.	1928	endemic	193733-1	LE
<i>Cistanche jodostoma</i> Butkov & Vved.	1961	non-endemic	661958-1	TASH003056

<i>Clausia gracillima</i> Popov ex Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978246-1	TASH001373
<i>Clausia tschimganica</i> Popov ex Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978247-1	TASH001379
<i>Convolvulus pseudocantabrica</i> subspec. <i>askabadensis</i> (Bornm. & Sint.) Vved.	1925	non-endemic	77188795-1	BM000832678
<i>Convolvulus tschimganicus</i> Popov & Vved.	1927	endemic	267145-1	TASH002660
<i>Cousinia allolepis</i> Tscherneva & Vved.	1962	endemic	198647-1	TASH003132
<i>Cousinia butkovii</i> Tschern. & Vved.	1961	endemic	198731-1	TASH003394
<i>Cousinia mogoltavica</i> Tschern. & Vved.	1961	endemic	199109-1	TASH003479
<i>Cousinia praestans</i> Tschern. & Vved.	1961	endemic	199211-1	TASH003523
<i>Cousinia pseudodshizakensis</i> Tschern. & Vved.	1961	endemic	199222-1	TASH003527
<i>Cousinia strobilocephala</i> Tscherneva & Vved.	1961	endemic	199350-1	TASH003145
<i>Crepis distincta</i> Popov & Vved.	1933	endemic	199820-1	TASH003679
<i>Cymatocarpus popovii</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1955	endemic	281908-1	TASH001199
<i>Dianthus angrenicus</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978238-1	TASH001031
<i>Dianthus brevipetalus</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978239-1	TASH001035
<i>Dianthus helenae</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978240-1	TASH001042
<i>Dianthus ugamicus</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978241-1	TASH001056
<i>Dictamnus tadshikorum</i> Vved.	1949	non-endemic	772379-1	LE
<i>Dipcadi turkestanicum</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	534000-1	TASH000557
<i>Eminium regelii</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	87000-1	TASH000205
<i>Epilobium acradenum</i> Pazij & Vved.	1959	non-endemic	611567-1	TASH002164
<i>Epilobium turkestanicum</i> Pazij & Vved.	1959	endemic	612410-1	TASH002166
<i>Eremostachys anisochila</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446770-1	TASH002863
<i>Eremostachys codonocalyx</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446786-1	TASH
<i>Eremostachys eriolarynx</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446799-1	TASH002882
<i>Eremostachys impressa</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446814-1	TASH000205
<i>Eremostachys integior</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446815-1	LE
<i>Eremostachys isochila</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446816-1	TASH000236
<i>Eremostachys labiosissima</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446824-1	TASH002788
<i>Eremostachys leiocalyx</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446829-1	TASH002791

<i>Eremostachys sogdiana</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	446863-1	TASH002792
<i>Eremurus ambigens</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	534671-1	LE
<i>Eremurus ammophilus</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	534672-1	LE
<i>Eremurus brachystemon</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	534682-1	TASH000223
<i>Eremurus candidus</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	534685-1	TASH000224
<i>Eremurus cristatus</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	534692-1	TASH000228
<i>Eremurus dolichomischus</i> Vved. & Wendelbo	1966	non-endemic	534693-1	W-2780
<i>Eremurus fuscus</i> (O. Fedtsch.) Vved.	1952	non-endemic	534696-1	LE
<i>Eremurus hilariae</i> Popov & Vved.	1924	endemic	534700-1	TASH061356
<i>Eremurus hissaricus</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	534702-1	TASH000232
<i>Eremurus iae</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	534703-1	TASH000236
<i>Eremurus lachnostegius</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	534713-1	LE
<i>Eremurus micranthus</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	534718-1	LE
<i>Eremurus pubescens</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	534726-1	TASH
<i>Eremurus regelii</i> Vved.	1928	endemic	534728-1	LE
<i>Eremurus roseolus</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	534730-1	LE
<i>Eremurus subalbiflorus</i> Vved.	1971	non-endemic	534740-1	TASH000243
<i>Eremurus tadshikorum</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	534743-1	LE
<i>Eremurus tianschanicus</i> Pazij & Vved. ex Pavlov	1958	endemic	534747-1	TASH000248
<i>Eremurus zenaidae</i> Vved.	1952	endemic	534753-1	TASH
<i>Eremurus zoeae</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	534754-1	TASH000251
<i>Erysimum chrysanthum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978243-1	TASH001258
<i>Erysimum clausioides</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	283714-1	TASH001262
<i>Erysimum ferganicum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	283799-1	TASH001269
<i>Erysimum gypsaceum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978244-1	TASH001273
<i>Erysimum jodonyx</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978245-1	TASH001278
<i>Erysimum microtrichon</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	283988-1	TASH001282
<i>Erysimum nuratense</i> Popov ex Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	284025-1	TASH001288
<i>Erysimum popovii</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	284093-1	TASH001289
<i>Fritillaria olgae</i> Vved.	1932	endemic	535249-1	TASH000492
<i>Gagea capillifolia</i> Vved.	1923	non-endemic	535467-1	TASH000260
<i>Gagea circumplexa</i> Vved.	1952	non-endemic	535479-1	TASH000261
<i>Gagea delicatula</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	535495-1	TASH000267
<i>Gagea exilis</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	535512-1	TASH000270
<i>Gagea gageoides</i> (Zucc.) Vved.	1932	non-endemic	535521-1	G
<i>Gagea graminifolia</i> Vved.	1932	non-endemic	535530-1	TASH000276

<i>Gagea gymnopoda</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	535538-1	TASH000277
<i>Gagea incrustata</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	535552-1	TASH000283
<i>Gagea kopetdagensis</i> Vved.	1932	endemic	535562-1	LE
<i>Gagea minutissima</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	535589-1	LE
<i>Gagea paedophila</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	535605-1	LE
<i>Gagea parva</i> Vved. ex Grossh.	1935	non-endemic	535608-1	TASH000295
<i>Gagea popovii</i> Vved.	1925	endemic	535621-1	TASH000298
<i>Gagea praemixta</i> Vved.	1977	endemic	77176982-1	TASH000308
<i>Gagea pseudoreticulata</i> Vved.	1932	non-endemic	535627-1	TASH000310
<i>Gagea subtilis</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	535669-1	TASH000320
<i>Gagea triquetra</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	535669-1	TASH000323
<i>Gagea vegeta</i> Vved.	1946	non-endemic	535706-1	TASH000327
<i>Gagea villosula</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	535710-1	LE
<i>Geranium charlesii</i> (Aitch. & Hemsl.) Vved.	1937	non-endemic	372883-1	BM000606788
<i>Geranium transversale</i> Vved. ex Pavlov	1934	non-endemic	373752-1	MW
<i>Gypsophila ferganica</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978233-1	TASH001009
<i>Gypsophila knorringiana</i> (Schischk.) Vved.	1953	endemic	154509-1	LE
<i>Haplophyllum ciscaucasicum</i> (Rupr.) Grossh. & Vved.	1949	non-endemic	773861-1	TASH000205
<i>Haplophyllum ferganicum</i> Vved.	1948	endemic	773865-1	TASH002053
<i>Haplophyllum foliosum</i> Vved.	1948	endemic	773866-1	TASH000232
<i>Haplophyllum leptomerum</i> Lincz. & Vved.	1949	non-endemic	773877-1	TASH002061
<i>Haplophyllum multicaule</i> Vved.	1949	endemic	773883-1	TASH002063
<i>Haplophyllum ramosissimum</i> (Paulsen) Vved.	1949	endemic	773889-1	LE
<i>Haplophyllum tenuisectum</i> Lincz. & Vved.	1949	non-endemic	773897-1	TASH002066
<i>Hedysarum setosum</i> Vved.	1952	non-endemic	498104-1	TASH001980
<i>Hyacinthus saviczii</i> (Woron.) Vved.	1932	non-endemic	536826-1	TBI
<i>Hypogomphia bucharica</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	447910-1	TASH002852
<i>Hypogomphia purpurea</i> (Regel) Vved. ex Kochk.	1986	endemic	943708-1	LE
<i>Iris amankutanica</i> O. Fedtsch. ex Vved.	1924	endemic	77241657-1	LE
<i>Iris brevituba</i> (Maxim.) Vved.	1951	non-endemic	438439-1	LE
<i>Iris kopetdagensis</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	438765-1	TASH
<i>Iris magnifica</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	438839-1	TASH000609
<i>Iris maracandica</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	438845-1	TASH000612
<i>Iris popovii</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	438982-1	TASH001288
<i>Iris subdecolorata</i> Vved.	1923	endemic	439145-1	TASH000617
<i>Iris tadshikorum</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	439159-1	LE

<i>Iris thianschanica</i> (Maxim.) Vved.	1932	non-endemic	439179-1	LE
<i>Iskandera alaiica</i> (Korsh.) Botsch. & Vved.	1955	endemic	285888-1	LE
<i>Ixiolirion ferganicum</i> Kovalevsk. & Vved.	1961	endemic	65679-1	TASH000584
<i>Juno baldshuanica</i> (O. Fedtsch. & B. Fedtsch.) Vved.	1963	non-endemic	439666-1	LE
<i>Juno bucharica</i> (Foster) Vved.	1941	non-endemic	439667-1	P01846412
<i>Juno capnoides</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	439668-1	TASH000599
<i>Juno hippolyti</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	439678-1	TASH0000314
<i>Juno inconspicua</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	439680-1	TASH000604
<i>Juno leptorrhiza</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	439684-1	LE00050076
<i>Juno linifolia</i> (O. Fedtsch.) Vved.	1935	endemic	439685-1	LE
<i>Juno narbuti</i> (O. Fedtsch.) Vved.	1941	endemic	439689-1	LE00050088
<i>Juno narynensis</i> (O. Fedtsch.) Vved.	1941	endemic	439690-1	LE00050091
<i>Juno nicolai</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	439691-1	TASH000613
<i>Juno orchioides</i> (Carrière) Vved.	1941	endemic	439693-1	BM001191245
<i>Juno parvula</i> Vved.	1963	endemic	439696-1	TASH000615
<i>Juno rosenbachiana</i> (Regel) Vved.	1935	non-endemic	439704-1	LE00050101
<i>Juno svetlanae</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	439710-1	TASH000616
<i>Juno tubergeniana</i> (Foster) Vved.	1941	endemic	439712-1	LE00050146
<i>Juno vicaria</i> Vved.	1963	endemic	439714-1	TASH000598
<i>Juno warleyensis</i> (Foster) Vved.	1941	endemic	439716-1	Lectotype: [Icon] "Iris warleyensis" in Foster, Gard.Chron., ser. 3, 31: 386, f. 134. 1902 (lectotype designated by Boltenkov 2016: 231)
<i>Juno willmottiana</i> (Foster) Vved.	1941	endemic	439717-1	Lectotype [Icon]: <i>Iris willmottiana</i> in Foster (1901: fig. 100) (lectotype designated by Boltenkov (2016: 231)
<i>Juno zenaidae</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	439721-1	TASH000619
<i>Korovinia tenuisecta</i> (Regel & Schmalh.) Nevski & Vved.	1937	non-endemic	843908-1	LE
<i>Lagochilus gypsaceus</i> var. <i>linearilobus</i> Vved. ex Zuckerw.	1985	endemic	918980-1	TASH
<i>Lagochilus gypsaceus</i> Vved.	1961	endemic	448727-1	TASH002901
<i>Lagochilus hirsutissimus</i> Vved.	1961	endemic	448728-1	TASH002900

<i>Lagochilus intermedius</i> Vved.	1961	endemic	448738-1	TASH002903
<i>Lagochilus pubescens</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	448756-1	TASH002905
<i>Lagochilus setulosus</i> Vved.	1955	endemic	448761-1	TASH002907
<i>Lepidium subcordatum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978255-1	TASH001159
<i>Linum heterosepalum</i> subsp. <i>tianschanicum</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978255-1	TASH003956
<i>Malcolmia malacotricha</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1952	endemic	286715-1	TASH001309
<i>Malcolmia pamirica</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1952	non-endemic	286721-1	TASH001314
<i>Malcolmia spryginoides</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1952	non-endemic	286726-1	TASH001318
<i>Matthiola czerniakowskiae</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978252-1	TASH001324
<i>Melandrium glaberrimum</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	155293-1	TASH001007
<i>Melandrium turkestanicum</i> (Regel) Vved.	1953	endemic	155388-1	LE
<i>Mesostemma karatavicum</i> (Schischk.) Vved.	1941	endemic	961833-1	LE
<i>Mesostemma kotschyannum</i> (Fenzl ex Boiss.) Vved.	1941	non-endemic	961834-1	LE
<i>Micromeria gontscharovii</i> Vved.	1961	non-endemic	451781-1	LE
<i>Micromeria popovii</i> (B. Fedtsch. & Gontsch.) Vved.	1961	non-endemic	451863-1	LE
<i>Mulgedium roseum</i> Popov & Vved.	1925	no information	233741-1	TASH003656
<i>Nevskiella gracillima</i> (Bunge) V.I. Krecz. & Vved.	1934	non-endemic	409502-1	LE
<i>Onobrychis amoena</i> Popov & Vved.,	1927	non-endemic	509836-1	TASH001989
<i>Oryzopsis tianschanica</i> Drobow & Vved.	1941	non-endemic	410235-1	TASH000055
<i>Otostegia glabricalyx</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	453639-1	TASH002910
<i>Otostegia megastegia</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	453646-1	TASH002913
<i>Oxytropis aulieatensis</i> Vved.	1948	endemic	511307-1	TASH001864
<i>Oxytropis echidna</i> Vved.	1925	endemic	511442-1	TASH001869
<i>Oxytropis ervicarpa</i> Vved. ex Z.N. Filimonova	1982	endemic	900445-1	TASH001874
<i>Oxytropis jucunda</i> Vved.	1948	endemic	511565-1	TASH001876
<i>Oxytropis pilosissima</i> Vved.	1948	endemic	511775-1	TASH003919
<i>Parrya angrenica</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978248-1	TASH001332
<i>Parrya crassifolia</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	287963-1	TASH001335
<i>Parrya darvazica</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1965	endemic	287964-1	LE
<i>Parrya minuta</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	287992-1	TASH001347
<i>Parrya nuratensis</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978249-1	TASH001351

<i>Parrya pamirica</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1965	non-endemic	287995-1	LE
<i>Parrya saxifraga</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978250-1	TASH001349
<i>Parrya subscapigera</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	288018-1	TASH001355
<i>Parrya villosula</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978251-1	TASH001357
<i>Pedicularis alata</i> Stadlm. ex Vved.	1955	endemic	806750-1	H
<i>Pedicularis allorrhampha</i> Vved.	1961	endemic	806758-1	TASH003042
<i>Pedicularis amoeniflora</i> Vved.,	1955	endemic	806768-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis argutiserrata</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	806793-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis chroorrhyncha</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	806908-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis gypsicola</i> Vved.	1959	endemic	807121-1	TASH003047
<i>Pedicularis hyperborea</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	807164-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis inconspicua</i> Vved.	1955	endemic	807178-1	TASH003049
<i>Pedicularis macrochila</i> Vved.	1925	endemic	807314-1	TASH003050
<i>Pedicularis pallasii</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	186447-2	LE
<i>Pedicularis popovii</i> Vved.	1955	endemic	807486-1	TASH003051
<i>Pedicularis pubiflora</i> Vved.	1955	endemic	807526-1	TASH003052
<i>Pedicularis schistostegia</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	807614-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis sibirica</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	807638-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis talassica</i> Vved.	1955	endemic	807699-1	TASH003054
<i>Pedicularis uralensis</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	807773-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis verae</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	807781-1	LE
<i>Pedicularis willdenovii</i> Vved.	1955	non-endemic	186481-2	LE
<i>Petilium eduardii</i> (Regel) Vved.	1941	non-endemic	539769-1	LE
<i>Phlomidosema parviflorum</i> (Benth.) Vved.	1941	non-endemic	453773-1	M
<i>Phlomis hypoleuca</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	453913-1	TASH002813
<i>Phlomis tschimganica</i> Vved.	1954	non-endemic	454096-1	TASH002828
<i>Phlomis tythaster</i> Vved.	1954	non-endemic	454100-1	TASH002827
<i>Phyteuma occultans</i> Popov & Vved.	1925	endemic	144436-1	TASH003123
<i>Platytaenia pamirica</i> (Lipsky) Nevski & Vved.	1937	non-endemic	847195-1	LE
<i>Platytaenia tragioides</i> (Boiss.) Nevski & Vved.	1937	non-endemic	847201-1	G-BOISS
<i>Prionotrichon erysimoides</i> (Kar. & Kir.) Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	288191-1	MW
<i>Prionotrichon pseudoparrya</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	288193-1	TASH001256
<i>Pyrethrum santoanum</i> Krasch., Popov & Vved.	1928	endemic	240929-1	TASH003261
<i>Rhammatophyllum frutex</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1952	endemic	288565-1	TASH001251
<i>Rhinopetalum arianum</i> Losinsk. & Vved.	1935	non-endemic	540388-1	LE

<i>Rhinopetalum gibbosum</i> (Boiss.) Losinsk. & Vved.	1935	non-endemic	540392-1	G-BOISS
<i>Salvia submutica</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1954	endemic	457324-1	TASH002972
<i>Saponaria gypsacea</i> Vved.	1941	endemic	978242-1	TASH001137
<i>Saponaria spathulifolia</i> (Fenzl) Vved.	1935	endemic	156659-1	LE
<i>Saussurea hypargyrea</i> Lipsch. & Vved.	1954	non-endemic	242312-1	LE
<i>Scutellaria andrachnoides</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	458127-1	TASH002738
<i>Scutellaria angrenica</i> Juz. & Vved.	1954	endemic	458129-1	TASH003775
<i>Scutellaria glabrata</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	458287-1	TASH002744
<i>Scutellaria heterotricha</i> Juz. & Vved.	1951	endemic	458325-1	LE
<i>Scutellaria nevskii</i> Juz. & Vved.	1951	endemic	458489-1	LE
<i>Scutellaria popovii</i> Vved.	1954	endemic	458578-1	TASH002762
<i>Scutellaria rubromaculata</i> Juz. & Vved.	1951	endemic	458625-1	LE
<i>Scutellaria urticifolia</i> Juz. & Vved.	1954	endemic	458738-1	LE
<i>Scutellaria velutina</i> Juz. & Vved.	1954	endemic	458746-1	TASH002778
<i>Silene acutidentata</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	156737-1	TASH000943
<i>Silene eviscosa</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	157315-1	TASH000969
<i>Silene excedens</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	non-endemic	157319-1	TASH000968
<i>Silene fedtschenkoi</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	157338-1	TASH000973
<i>Silene megalantha</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	157792-1	LE
<i>Silene monantha</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	157848-1	LE
<i>Silene paranadena</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	158010-1	TASH000991
<i>Silene pubicalyx</i> Bondarenko & Vved.	1971	endemic	158160-1	TASH000996
<i>Silene schischkinii</i> (Popov) Vved.	1953	endemic	158325-1	TASH003915
<i>Sophiopsis micrantha</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1952	non-endemic	289972-1	TASH001241
<i>Spergularia adenophora</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	957737-1	TASH000937
<i>Spergularia glaucophylla</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	978230-1	LE
<i>Spergularia microsperma</i> (Kindb.) Vved.	1953	non-endemic	158952-1	P00388961
<i>Spergularia microspermoides</i> Vved	1941	non-endemic	978231-1	LE
<i>Spergularia nematopoda</i> Vved.	1941	non-endemic	978232-1	LE
<i>Stachyopsis lamiiflora</i> (Rupr.) Popov & Vved.	1923	non-endemic	459252-1	LE
<i>Stachyopsis oblongata</i> (Schrenk) Popov & Vved.	1923	non-endemic	459254-1	LE

<i>Stroganowia angustifolia</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	290225-1	TASH001172
<i>Stroganowia longifolia</i> (Boiss.) Botsch. & Vved.	1948	non-endemic	290235-1	G
<i>Stroganowia minor</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978256-1	TASH001178
<i>Stroganowia tianschanica</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	endemic	290242-1	TASH001187
<i>Stubendorffia curvinervia</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1952	endemic	290250-1	TASH001192
<i>Stubendorffia pterocarpa</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978257-1	TASH001193
<i>Tetracmidion glochidiatum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1941	endemic	978253-1	TASH001307
<i>Thymus subnervosus</i> Vved. Nabiev & Tulyag.	1987	no information	934225-1	TASH002985
<i>Trichanthemis radiata</i> Krasch. & Vved.	1929	endemic	256198-1	TASH003359
<i>Trichochiton umbrosum</i> Botsch. & Vved.	1948	non-endemic	290864-1	TASH001321
<i>Tulipa anisophylla</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	542823-1	LE
<i>Tulipa bifloriformis</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	542848-1	TASH000502
<i>Tulipa binutans</i> Vved.	1952	non-endemic	542850-1	TASH000503
<i>Tulipa carinata</i> Vved.	1971	non-endemic	542871-1	TASH000506
<i>Tulipa dasystemonoides</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	542898-1	TASH000507
<i>Tulipa dubia</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	542902-1	LE
<i>Tulipa dykesiana</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	542903-1	LE
<i>Tulipa ferganica</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	542911-1	TASH000508
<i>Tulipa hissarica</i> Popov & Vved.	1935	endemic	542948-1	TASH
<i>Tulipa karatavica</i> (Regel) Vved. ex Lipsch.	1932	non-endemic	542961-1	LE
<i>Tulipa korshinskyi</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	542969-1	LE
<i>Tulipa mogoltavica</i> Popov & Vved.	1971	non-endemic	543007-1	TASH000513
<i>Tulipa orithyoides</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	543025-1	TASH000514
<i>Tulipa orthopoda</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	543029-1	TASH000516
<i>Tulipa paradasystemon</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	543032-1	TASH
<i>Tulipa platystemon</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	543039-1	LE
<i>Tulipa prolongata</i> Vved.	1971	non-endemic	543047-1	LE
<i>Tulipa rosea</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	543063-1	TASH000520
<i>Tulipa subbiflora</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	543100-1	TASH000523
<i>Tulipa subpraestans</i> Vved.	1971	endemic	928395-1	TASH000524
<i>Tulipa subquinquefolia</i> Vved.	1946	endemic	543103-1	LE
<i>Tulipa zenaidae</i> Vved.	1935	non-endemic	543153-1	TASH000555
<i>Ungernia ferganica</i> Vved. ex Artjush.	1970	endemic	66973-1	TASH000513
<i>Ungernia minor</i> Vved.	1935	endemic	66975-1	LE

<i>Ungernia oligostroma</i> Popov & Vved.	1959	endemic	66977-1	TASH000578
<i>Ungernia tadschicorum</i> Vved. ex Artjush.	1970	endemic	66979-1	TASH000529
<i>Ungernia victoris</i> Vved. ex Artjush.	1970	endemic	66983-1	TASH000349
<i>Veronica mogoltavica</i> Popov ex Vved.	1925	non-endemic	812325-1	LE
<i>Veronica nanella</i> Vved.	1961	non-endemic	812358-1	TASH003025
<i>Veronica stylophora</i> Popov ex Vved.	1925	endemic	812697-1	TASH003028
<i>Viola alaica</i> Vved.	1928	endemic	867575-1	LE
<i>Xiphion winkleri</i> (Regel) Vved.	1941	endemic	442093-1	LE
<i>Ziziphora pedicellata</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	462010-1	TASH002979
<i>Ziziphora suffruticosa</i> Pazij & Vved.	1961	endemic	462028-1	TASH002981

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